

Forecasting the 2026 Hungarian Parliamentary Elections

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1 Forecast Results

The Hungarian public opinion polls exhibit clear clustering across polling companies. On the one hand, Alapjogokért Központ, Nézőpont, and Századvég consistently report a modest advantage for Fidesz, typically in the range of 5–10 percentage points. On the other hand, IDEA, Iránytű, Medián, Publicus, Republikon, and ZRI indicate a lead for Tisza, generally between 10 and 20 percentage points. Therefore, the forecast considers two scenarios: one in which all of the above-mentioned pollsters are included in the model, and another in which the Fidesz-leaning pollsters (Alapjogokért Központ, Nézőpont, and Századvég) are excluded.

Tisza's Lead Over Fidesz

Percentage Point Difference (%), According to Major Public Opinion Pollsters Across "Sure Voters"

Nézőpont (2026-03-24) and Publicus (2026-02-12, 2026-02-27) are averages of multiple polls published at the same time

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1.1 Base Scenario: All Polls Are Considered

The following figures present the forecasted outcomes under the baseline specification.

Forecasted National Party List Votes

Entry threshold for parliamentary representation (5%): 281,211 votes

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Fraction of Forecasted Single-Member District (OEKV) Votes by County

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Single-Member District (OEVK) Prediction

Percentage Points Difference between Tisza and Fidesz (%)

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Simulation Results

Party	Mean seats	95% CI	P(majority)	P(supermajority)
Tisza	110	59–149	66%	19%
Fidesz	81	43–133	23%	3%
MiHazánk	8	5–11	0%	0%
DK	0	0–0	0%	0%
MKKP	0	0–0	0%	0%
Other	0	0–0	0%	0%

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Number of Predicted Parliament Seats for Each Party

Tisza (110) Fidesz (81) MiHazánk (8)

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1.2 Filtered Scenario: Fidesz-Biased Polls Are Excluded

The following figures present the forecasted outcomes under the filtered specification.

Forecasted National Party List Votes: Without Fidesz-Biased Polls

Without Alapjogokért Központ, Nézőpont, and Századvég

Entry threshold for parliamentary representation (5%): 281,211 votes

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Fraction of Forecasted Single-Member District (OEVK) Votes by County: Without Fidesz-Biased Polls

Without Alapjogokért Központ, Nézőpont, and Századvég

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Single-Member District (OEVK) Prediction: Without Fidesz-Biased Polls

Percentage Points Difference between Tisza and Fidesz (%)

Without Alapjogokért Központ, Nézőpont, and Századvég

Map data: © NVI • Created with Datawrapper

Simulation Results: Without Fidesz-Biased Polls

Without Alapjogokért Központ, Nézőpont, and Századvég

Party	▼ Mean seats	95% CI	P(majority)	P(supermajority)
Tisza	128	76–156	89%	50%
Fidesz	63	35–115	7%	0%
MiHazánk	8	5–12	0%	0%
DK	0	0–0	0%	0%
MKKP	0	0–0	0%	0%
Other	0	0–0	0%	0%

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Number of Predicted Parliament Seats for Each Party: Without Fidesz-Biased Polls

Without Alapjogokért Központ, Nézőpont, and Századvég

■ Tisza (128) ■ Fidesz (63) ■ MiHazánk (8)

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2 Data

The analysis is based on two primary data sources: historical election results and public opinion polling data covering Hungarian parliamentary and European Parliament elections between 2014 and 2026.

Historical election data were obtained from the National Election Office ([Nemzeti Választási Iroda \[2026\]](#)) and include the 2014, 2018, and 2022 parliamentary elections and the 2019 and 2024 European Parliament elections. While European Parliament elections provide only national party list results, Hungarian parliamentary elections include both national list votes and single-member district (OEVK) results. Minority ethnic representation is excluded from the analysis due to its negligible parliamentary impact. The 2024 European Parliament results, originally reported at the polling station level, were aggregated to the OEVK level using the 2022 district structure. Parties are grouped into six categories (Fidesz, Tisza, MKKP, Mi Hazánk, DK, and Others), with the opposition coalition categorized as DK, when DK did not participate individually.

Public opinion polling data were obtained from the Vox Populi database ([Tóka \[2019\]](#)) and include polls conducted prior to the same set of elections. The sample consists of major Hungarian polling organizations that regularly publish election forecasts. Polls are expressed in percentage vote shares, and only estimates based on “sure voters” are included, except for a single Medián poll related to the 2022 European Parliament election, for which results were reported based on “all respondents”, as no “sure voter” estimate was available. For historical elections, only the final poll from each pollster is used, while for the 2026 election all polls from February 2026 onward are incorporated. To ensure comparability, polling data are categorized into the same six party groups as the election results.

A key limitation of the dataset is that the Tisza party, expected to be a major competitor in 2026, appears only in the 2024 European Parliament election, resulting in limited historical information relative to other parties.

3 Methodology

This study develops a probabilistic election forecasting model for the 2026 Hungarian parliamentary elections that integrates polling data, historical voting patterns, and Monte Carlo simulation to generate point and interval forecasts of seat distributions. The model proceeds in four stages: pollster evaluation and aggregation, probabilistic modeling of national vote shares, district-level projection, and seat allocation. The full pipeline is simulated 1000 times to obtain expected outcomes, confidence intervals, and probability estimates.

Pollster performance is evaluated using historical election data to estimate systematic bias and predictive accuracy. Bias for pollster j and party k is defined as the average deviation between poll estimates and actual

results, while predictive accuracy is measured using the root mean squared error (RMSE). A pooled industry-wide polling error σ_{poll} is also computed. Polls are first corrected for bias,

$$\text{poll}_{\text{corrected}}(i, k) = \text{poll}(i, k) - \text{Bias}(j, k), \quad (1)$$

and then aggregated using weights based on recency and accuracy,

$$w(i) = \exp(-\lambda \cdot \text{days}_i) \cdot \frac{1}{\text{RMSE}(j)^2}. \quad (2)$$

The resulting weighted average $\mu(k)$ represents the estimated national vote share for each party.

Uncertainty is incorporated by modeling vote shares as random variables. The standard deviation is defined as polling error adjusted for staleness,

$$\sigma(k) = \sigma_{\text{poll}}(1 + \alpha \cdot t_{\text{staleness}}). \quad (3)$$

To ensure that vote shares sum to 100%, a Dirichlet distribution is used. Parameters are defined as $\alpha_k = \mu_k \alpha_0$, where α_0 is calibrated to match target variance,

$$\text{Var} = \frac{\mu_k(1 - \mu_k)}{\alpha_0 + 1}. \quad (4)$$

This enforces coherence and negative correlations across parties.

National vote shares are translated into district-level outcomes using historical geographic patterns. For each district d and party k , a swing coefficient is computed as the average deviation from national results,

$$\bar{\Delta}(d, k) = \frac{1}{T} \sum_t (\text{Vote}_{d,t}(k) - \text{Vote}_{\text{national},t}(k)). \quad (5)$$

District vote shares are then projected as

$$\text{vote}(d, k) = \pi(k) + \bar{\Delta}(d, k) + \varepsilon_d, \quad (6)$$

where $\varepsilon_d \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma_d^2)$ captures local variation. Negative values are truncated and shares are renormalized. The noise parameter σ_d is calibrated by backtesting, using 2024 European Parliament results for swing estimation and 2022 parliamentary results as the validation benchmark.

Seats are allocated according to Hungarian electoral rules. In each of the 106 single-member districts, the

party with the highest vote share wins the seat. The remaining 93 list seats are distributed proportionally using the d'Hondt method based on national votes and compensation (fragment) votes. Turnout scenarios can be incorporated by scaling total valid votes.

The full model is simulated $n_{\text{sim}} = 1000$ times. In each simulation, national vote shares are drawn from the Dirichlet distribution, projected to districts, and converted into seats. Aggregated outputs include expected seat counts, 95% confidence intervals, and probabilities of achieving a majority (at least 100 seats) or supermajority (at least 133 seats), as well as district-level expected outcomes.

Model performance is evaluated via backtesting on the 2022 election using only pre-election polls, with bias estimated from earlier elections and district parameters calibrated from historical data. Simulated confidence intervals are compared to actual outcomes to assess calibration and the validity of uncertainty assumptions.

References

Nemzeti Választási Iroda (2026). Választási információs szolgálat. <https://vtr.valasztas.hu/nyito>.

Tóka, G. (2019). Választási közvélemény-kutatások magyarországon. Excel adatbázis. Elérhető: <https://kozvelemeney.wordpress.com>.